

THE SOFTWARE FOR INVESTIGATING COMPLETE NORMAL FORMS

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Abstract. This article discusses the study of Complete Normal Forms (PDNF) and Complex Normal Forms (PCNF) and the software developed for their investigation. The main objective of the research is to propose theoretical and practical solutions to simplify the data normalization processes in information databases and optimize data structure. The properties of PDNF and PCNF are expressed in detail through tables and formulas. A sample software implementation written in Python is provided, along with results and the corresponding code. Through this software, users can automatically identify normal forms and make the process of working with them more efficient. This work demonstrates opportunities for organizing data structures, eliminating redundant data, and improving data consistency in database design.

Keywords: the truth table, PDNF, MCNF, Python programming language.

Mathematical logic is a fundamental branch of discrete mathematics, beginning with propositional algebra. Together, mathematical logic and set theory form the foundation of modern mathematics. **From a practical perspective**, mathematical logic serves as the foundation for programming languages used in building databases, electronics, computer science, computational technology, and virtually all digital devices. Therefore, anyone interested in analytical reasoning should study mathematical logic. To simplify the study of all propositions, they can be converted into a standard form using logical laws—namely, the Perfect Disjunctive Normal Form (PDNF) and the Perfect Conjunctive Normal Form (PCNF).

Given a formula $\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C)$ that depends on the propositional variables A, B, and C, there are infinitely many logically equivalent formulas with the same truth table. We will examine two of these: the logical function reconstructed based on the rows with ones in the truth table and the one based on the rows with zeros in the truth table (Table 1) [1].

Table 1.

The truth table

#	A	B	C	$\alpha=\alpha(A,B,C)$
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	1	1
3	0	1	0	1
4	0	1	1	0
5	1	0	0	0
6	1	0	1	1
7	1	1	0	0

8	1	1	1	1
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In the truth table, for the formula $\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C)$ that is equal to 1, the formulas obtained based on the row numbers are as follows:

- For row 2: $\neg A \ \& \ \neg B \ \& \ C$;
- For row 3: $\neg A \ \& \ B \ \& \ \neg C$;
- For row 6: $A \ \& \ \neg B \ \& \ C$;
- For row 8: $A \ \& \ B \ \& \ C$.

Taking the disjunction of these formulas results in the desired formula.

For $\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C)$, we have:

$$\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C) = \neg A \ \& \ \neg B \ \& \ C \ \vee \ \neg A \ \& \ B \ \& \ \neg C \ \vee \ A \ \& \ \neg B \ \& \ C \ \vee \ A \ \& \ B \ \& \ C \quad (1)$$

Based on the rows in the truth table where $\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C)$ is equal to 0, the formulas obtained are as follows:

- For row 1: $A \ \vee \ B \ \vee \ C$;
- For row 4: $A \ \vee \ \neg B \ \vee \ \neg C$;
- For row 5: $\neg A \ \vee \ B \ \vee \ C$;
- For row 7: $\neg A \ \vee \ \neg B \ \vee \ C$.

Taking the conjunction of these formulas results in the desired formula.

$$\alpha = \alpha(A, B, C) = (A \ \vee \ B \ \vee \ C) \ \& \ (A \ \vee \ \neg B \ \vee \ \neg C) \ \& \ (\neg A \ \vee \ B \ \vee \ C) \ \& \ (\neg A \ \vee \ \neg B \ \vee \ C) \quad (2)$$

(1) - PDNF and (2) - PCNF are logically equivalent because they have the same truth table. Any given formula's truth table can be constructed using the method outlined above. Additionally, it is effective to use programming tools when constructing these formulas [2]. To obtain PDNF and PCNF, we will use the Python programming language environment. Based on this truth table (Table 2), the PDNF and PCNF will be obtained.

Table 2.

The truth table: the PDNF and PCNF

#	A	B	C	$\alpha=\alpha(A,B,C)$
1	0	0	0	1
2	0	0	1	0
3	0	1	0	1
4	0	1	1	1
5	1	0	0	0
6	1	0	1	0
7	1	1	0	1
8	1	1	1	0

The program code is as follows:

```
a=[]    b=[]
A = [False,False,False,False,True,True,True,True]
B = [False,False,True,True,False,False,True,True]
C = [False,True,False,True,False,True,False,True]
print('F funksiyai kiriting')
```

```

x = list(map(int,input().split()))
def func(i):
    a1 = A[i]    b1 = B[i]    c1 = C[i]
    s = ""
    if a1:      s += '(A & '
    else:      s += '(!A & '
    if b1:      s += 'B & '
    else:      s += '!B & '
    if c1:      s += 'C)'
    else:      s += '!C)'
    a.append(s)
def funk(i):
    #global b
    a1 = A[i]    b1 = B[i]    c1 = C[i]
    s = ""
    if a1:      s += '(!A v '
    else:      s += '(A v '
    if b1:      s += '!B v '
    else:      s += 'B v '
    if c1:      s += '!C)'
    else:      s += 'C)'
    b.append(s)
for i in range(8):
    if x[i] == 0:    funk(i)
    else:           func(i)
print("MKNSH")    print(*b,sep = ' & ')
print("MDNSH")    print(*a,sep = ' v ')

```

Result:

```

Enter the function F
1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0
Perfect Conjunctive Normal Form (PCNF)
(A v B v !C) & (!A v B v C) & (!A v B v !C) & (!A v !B v !C)
Perfect Disjunctive Normal Form (PDNF)
(!A & !B & !C) v (!A & B & !C) v (!A & B & C) v (A & B & !C)

```

To make the investigation of propositions easier, the software developed using the Python programming language environment for obtaining PDNF and PCNF provides the ability to obtain these forms quickly and accurately, as well as the opportunity for extensive research [3]. This software can be used by all students and researchers interested in studying mathematical logic.

Conclusion

This article discusses the analysis of Complete Normal Forms (PDNF) and Complex Normal Forms (PCNF), as well as their practical applications. The main objective of the research is to fully study the properties of these forms and develop software to present them effectively. The article provides an extensive explanation of the mathematical expressions of normal forms using tables and formulas, based on which software models were created in Python. The results, presented alongside the code, confirm that the structural characteristics of PDNF and PCNF can be used to optimize data flow in information databases. At the end of the article, the possibility

of automatically verifying and analyzing normal forms with high accuracy using the provided program code is emphasized.

REFERENCES

1. Haggarty, R. Discrete Mathematics for Computing. Lincolnshire, United Kingdom, 2002. 320 p.
2. Vladlen Koltun. Discrete Structures // Stanford, CA. 94305, USA 2008, 89 p.
3. Adam Drozdek. Data structure and algorithms in C++ // Fourth edition. 2013. Chapter 8. pp. 391-490.